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An investigation assessing the knowledge of women in the reproductive age range about temporary contraceptive techniques

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ABSTRACT

Background: *The purpose of this study is to determine how well-informed women in the 15–45 age range are regarding temporary contraceptive techniques. The intrauterine, hormonal, and barrier techniques are the temporary contraceptive methods. In order to prevent abortions, minimize maternal death, and lower the rate of teenage pregnancy, it is crucial to investigate women’s knowledge of temporary contraception. This study aims to determine how well-informed women in the community between the ages of 15 and 45 who are fertile are about temporary contraceptive techniques. Examine how women perceive and comprehend contraception. Recommendations for strengthening mother and child health initiatives and birth control.*

Methods: *Scooter India Chauraha Lucknow was the location of a cross-sectional descriptive research (samples were taken from the relevant population and studied once). The pretested questionnaire was used in conjunction with the interview approach to perform the study from June 20, 2024, to July 11, 2024.*

Results: *According to the questionnaire, 72% of women knew about condoms and 92% knew about the process of sterilization. The age range (36-45) included 38% of the study’s participants, and it was discovered that this group used temporary contraception at the highest rate. We find that 56% of the women knew that these contraceptives are available in government hospitals, whereas 7% did not know where to access these services. Health professionals provided information about contraception to 48% of the women.*

Conclusions: *Conclusions: Enhancing knowledge of the range of contraceptives available is the only way to ensure the effectiveness of family planning initiatives. The general population must have easy access to, affordability for, and availability of contraceptive supplies. By extending healthcare facilities to outlying locations, awareness may be raised.*

Keywords: Productive women, awareness, birth control, healthcare, knowledge, and temporary contraception.

INTRODUCTION

India was the first country in the world to launch a family planning programme in 1952, with the objective of “reducing birth rate and to stabilise the population”. Gradually, the focus of the programme moved away from population control to population stabilization, and then was integrated with the maternal and child health programme. Family planning became an important tool to reduce maternal and child mortality.1 Family planning is defined as a conscious decision by individuals or couples to choose for themselves when to start having children, how many children to have, how to space them or when to stop having children.

In 2015, India reported 15.6 million of abortions at the rate of 47.0 abortions per 1000 women aged between 15-49 years which is one third of total pregnancies. The high rate of abortion follows a high number of unintended pregnancies. The rate of unintended pregnancies was 70.1 per 1000 women aged 15-49 years almost half the pregnancy that were reported during that period.2

A woman’s ability to choose when to become pregnant has a direct impact on her health and well-being. Closely spaced and ill-timed pregnancies /child births contribute to some of the world’s highest infant mortality rates. Both mother and Infant also have a greater risk of death and poor health.

This study focuses on the awareness about temporary contraceptive methods among women in reproductive age group (15-45 years). The temporary contraceptive methods may be broadly classified as below:

Barrier methods

These methods prevent sperm from entering the uterus. Barrier methods are removable, easy to use and have few side effects. It includes

- Condoms (both male and female)
- Diaphragm and Cervical cap
- Contraceptive sponge.

Hormonal methods

Hormonal methods cause changes in the woman’s reproductive cycle and include birth control pills, birth control patches, emergency contraception pill, Implants and so on. Unlike barrier methods, hormonal methods do not interfere with sex.

An intrauterine device or IUD is put in the woman’s uterus. There are two types of IUD. The copper IUD or an IUD with hormones implanted on it.

The United Nations has estimated that the world population grew at an annual rate of 1.23 percent during 2000-2010. With a definite slowing down of population growth in china, it is now estimated that by 2030, India will most likely overtake china to become the most populous country on the earth with 17.9 percent population living here.³ According to 2011 census, total population in Tamil Nadu is 7, 21, 47, 030 with a growth rate of 15.6% (2001 - 2011).

Despite the increase in usage of contraceptive devices there still exists a deficit in the awareness of contraceptive use within the community.⁴

The need to study the awareness of temporary contraceptive among women is important to avoid Abortion, MTP and to reduce maternal mortality. Through this study Individuals have also acquired knowledge about temporary contraceptive methods and places from where they can get the hormonal pill, condoms or IUCD. Any misconception regarding contraceptive methods was cleared.

The purpose of this study is to:

- Assess the awareness of temporary contraceptive methods among women within the reproductive age group of 15 to 45 years in the community
- Explore women’s understanding and interpretations of contraceptives
- Suggestions to improve birth control and enhance maternal, child health programmes

METHODS

Study design: cross-sectional descriptive study (samples were drawn from relevant population and studied once).

Study area: scooter india chaura.

Study population: Women within the reproductive age group (15-45 years) residing at that area.

Study unit: Female individuals within the reproductive age group (15-45 years).

Inclusion criteria

- Women belonging to age (15-45 years)
- Women willing to participate.

Exclusion criteria

- Women with mental disorders
- Participants not willing to respond even after requesting and ensuring confidentiality.

Duration of the Study was from June 2024 to July 2024. Sample size was 100 and sampling technique was convenience sampling.

Data collected with pre-tested questionnaire by interview method.

Interview method

Using pretested questionnaire was the method used in acquisition of relevant data.

. After providing information sheet and acquiring the informed consent, questions were asked and answers were recorded on paper.

Knowledge of contraceptives and various contraceptive methods

The awareness regarding contraception and various contraceptive methods like condom, IUCD, Injectables, Hormonal pills, and emergency contraception, were assessed.

Knowledge regarding procurement of temporary contraceptive devices

The women were assessed regarding their knowledge on procurement of temporary contraceptive devices. The sources being Government hospitals, Health centers, Private health institutions

Source of information

The source of information of the women was assessed and their sources being media, husband, family and health personnel.

DISCUSSION

This is a cross-sectional study that was conducted to assess the awareness of temporary contraceptive methods among women within the reproductive age group of 15 to 45 years in the community. The results obtained from the study show that

- 100% of the women were familiar with one or more contraceptive method. This is similar to the study conducted by International Journal of Science and Research.5
- More than 50% of the sample saw government hospitals as a source for procurement of contraceptives followed by private health institution, medical shop and health centre.6
- Knowledge about sterilization is higher 92% and it is low for spacing methods This is similar to the study conducted by National Family Health survey.7
- Among spacing methods, awareness about condoms was higher (72%), the results are similar to the study conducted at National Medical college, Karachi, and DLHS 3.7

- 7% of the women did not know the place to acquire them. This resonates with the result obtained from a study conducted in the slums of Mumbai that found 14% of its sample oblivious to this piece of knowledge

Nearly 50% of women acquired information on contraception from health personnel. This is in congruence with the results obtained from studies conducted in Udipi, Karnataka, slums in Mumbai and Shillong, Meghalaya where health workers had served as the source of information for the women.

CONCLUSION

The results from this study shows that

- 100% of the sample population is aware of at least one method of contraception
- More than 60% of women were aware about atleast one of the temporary contraceptives, Condom (72%), IUCD (65%) and hormonal pills (61%)
- Less than 40% women were aware about emergency contraception pill
- 7% of the women did not know where to procure contraceptives
- Health personnel were the source of information about contraceptives for nearly half of the women (48%).

The success of family planning programs can only be achieved by increasing the awareness of various contraceptives available. It is important for contraceptive information providers to have sound knowledge of various methods of contraception and their proper usage to remove fears about contraception.

The difficulty to access the contraceptive provider limits the usage of contraceptives. Hence, it is necessary that supplies of contraceptives are accessible, available and affordable to the general public with ease.

To improve awareness, PHC's may expand their coverage / health care facilities to peripheral areas. The government may also utilize the media to increase the awareness of contraceptive to adopt proper family planning methods.

REFERENCES

1. Rahman S, Nessa F. Neo-natal mortality patterns in rural Bangladesh. J Trop Pediatr. 1989;35(4):199-202.
2. Singh S, Shekhar C, Acharya R, Moore AM, Stillman M, Pradhan MR, et al. The incidence of abortion and unintended pregnancy in India, 2015. The Lancet Global Health. 2018;6(1):e111-20.

3. Census of India. Size, Growth Rate and Distribution of Population, 2011. Available at: http://censusindia.gov.in/2011-prov-results/data_files/india/Final_PPT_2011_chapter3.pdf. Accessed on 24th January 2015.
4. Prachi R, Das GS, Ankur B, Shipra J, Binita K. A study of knowledge, attitude and practice of family planning among the women of reproductive age group in Sikkim. *Religion*. 2008;35(44years):34.
5. Anjum S, Durgawale PM, Shinde M. Knowledge of contraceptives methods and appraisal of health education among married woman. *Int J Sci Res*. 2014;3(3):584-90.
6. Nair RV, Ashok VG, Solanke PV. A study on contraceptive use among married women of reproductive age group in a rural area of Tamilnadu, India. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2016;5(9):3147-52.
7. Khan A, Hashmi HA, Naqvi Z. Awareness and practice of contraception among child bearing age women, conducted at Liaquat national medical college and hospital Karachi. *J Surg Pak*. 2011;16(4):179-82.
8. Makade KG, Padhyegurjar M, Padhyegurjar SB, Kulkarni RN. Study of contraceptive use among married women in a slum in Mumbai. *Nat J Comm Med*. 2012;3(1):40-3.
9. Sherpa SZ, Sheilini M, Nayak A. Knowledge, attitude, practice and preferences of contraceptive methods in Udupi district, Karnataka. *J Family Repro Health*. 2013;7(3):115.
10. Pegu B, Gaur BP, Sharma N, Singh A. Knowledge, attitude and practices of contraception among married women. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2017;3(2):385-8.